

A Study of Needs Assessment for Faculty Development in Government Higher Education Institutes located in Delhi

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Abstract- Faculty development (FD) is a crucial factor in achieving institutional excellence. Through faculty development programs (FDPs), not only are faculty members supported in updating their knowledge and fulfilling their multifaceted roles as educators, researchers, and leaders, but institutional effectiveness is also accomplished. However, it has been observed that these programs are organised according to the availability of resources and the convenience of the program designers without systematically identifying faculty needs. The present study, based on a review of the literature, presents the perceptions of higher education faculty members regarding the need assessment for FDPs. Findings emphasise that data-driven needs assessments form the foundation for relevant and impactful faculty development in the higher education system.

Keywords: faculty development, needs assessment, higher education, professional development, academic staff training, institutional effectiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of higher education, faculty members are expected to fulfil their diverse and complex roles. Batra and Ahmad (2010) suggested, "In the present era of globalisation and privatisation, it has become extremely essential that the teachers are provided full support for their academic development and recognition so that they are fully prepared and encouraged to face any challenge of higher education." Gardiner (2000) has explored, "High-quality faculty professional development for every teacher is an urgent need and will become essential to institutions' capacity to compete for students in the years ahead and to survive and thrive.

We have a wide array of new knowledge about student learning and development, and we have research-based methods of fostering this learning and development. If used, this knowledge and these methods can permit us to produce learning on a scale never before achieved..."

The faculty's performance is directly related to the students' learning outcomes, research productivity, and overall institutional effectiveness. Consequently, faculty development (FD) has become a strategic

priority for universities seeking to enhance academic excellence and respond to global challenges such as technological innovations, changing pedagogical paradigms, and accountability in higher education (Austin & Sorcinelli, 2013; Sorcinelli, dy, & Beach, 2006). A well-designed FD program begins with a systematic needs assessment — a structured process of identifying gaps between existing faculty competencies and desired performance standards (Witkin & Altschuld, 1995). Conducting such an assessment ensures that professional development initiatives are appropriate, evidence-based, and aligned with institutional goals. Despite its recognised importance, many institutions continue to implement faculty development activities without a formal or comprehensive assessment of actual needs (Travis, 1993; Steinert et al., 2006). This study, therefore, explores the developmental requirements of the faculty to strengthen faculty development system in the whole arena of higher education.

To keep pace with the upcoming knowledge in the same area or in integrated areas, it is important that development programmes for faculty be conducted regularly. "... no competitive advantage lasts. Only change and regeneration continue to keep the system thriving and kicking."(Chandra B.P. Singh (2008))

Indian policy makers recognized the significance of faculty development programmes since independence. The University Education Commission (1948-49), headed by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, recommended refresher courses for high school and intermediate college teachers to be organized by each university. Since that time, many recommendations were made by various educationists, commissions and committees formed for development of Higher Education but the turning point came in 1987 when the University Grants Commission introduced the Academic Staff Orientation Scheme (ASOS) to provide exposure to issues and new ideas relating to education as a profession.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Kearney (1994) has concluded that staff development, as a fundamental element of institutional quality, must encompass all types of training necessary for enhanced effectiveness and efficiency.

Witkin & Altschuld (1995) have described that needs assessment in faculty development programs involves a systematic process of identifying and prioritizing areas where faculty members require enhancement in skills, knowledge, or attitudes to perform effectively in evolving academic contexts. According to Sorcinelli et al. (2006), need assessment serves multiple purposes, like guiding program design, allocating resources efficiently, and providing a baseline for later evaluation. Steinert et al. (2006) emphasized that faculty development initiatives grounded in identified needs are more likely to achieve behavioural change and institutional impact than those developed ad hoc.

Empirical studies consistently reported several recurring domains of faculty needs. The integration of educational technology and the capacity for online or blended learning delivery emerged as major developmental priorities during the early 2010s (Cook, Steinert, & Boillat, 2013). In addition, scholars identified needs in research skills, scholarship of teaching and learning (SoTL), and academic leadership for mid-career and senior

faculty (Gibbs & Coffey, 2004; O'Sullivan & Irby, 2011).

Francisco (2006) has guided that implementation of learning management systems in educational institutions need that technical and institutional barriers be overcome.

Intree et al. (2007) have suggested that knowledge management process should be a main principle in staff development leading to organizational development in keeping up the global social economic growth.

Opre et al. (2008) in their study conducted on four Romanian universities found that participants perceived the detailed knowledge of one's own line of specialisation, teaching skills improvement and improvement of one's performance in publishing/presenting the results of research, as areas of relevance for FDPs.

The Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS), 2010 conducted by the OECD in its report, has identified major teaching factors – Curricular, teacher-orchestrated classroom management, teaching strategy, monitoring, assessment, etc. Pedagogical content knowledge has been seen as having a place in continuous professional development.

Austin & Sorcinelli (2013) highlighting the diversity of faculty roles, argue that one-size-fits-all development models fail to address the differing needs of early-career, adjunct, and senior academics. Steinert et al., 2016; Amundsen & Wilson, 2012 have challenged that many need assessment studies rely primarily on self-reported data, lack longitudinal follow-up, and measure only participant satisfaction rather than changes in teaching practice or student learning.

Hence, it is concluded that available literature establishes that systematic needs assessment is fundamental to designing effective faculty development in higher education.

III. PRESENT SCENARIO OF THE ACADEMIC STAFF ORIENTATION SCHEME IN INDIA

As per the present rules, anybody who has a good academic record with at least 55% marks in the post-graduate level education and has qualified UGC National Eligibility Test for lecturers may apply for a teaching position in a higher education institute. Appointment is based on one's performance in the interview. As such, there is no prescribed requirement to have any pre-job training for appointment as a teacher in any higher education institute. In order to fill this gap, the Academic Staff Colleges, established by the University Grants Commission (UGC) conduct specially designed Academic Staff Orientation Programmes for newly appointed teachers and Refresher Courses for in-service teachers in the higher education system.

Apart from Academic Staff Orientation Programmes, various higher education institutes organize faculty development programmes under Quality Assurance Schemes either funded by AICTE or self-sustained models. Moreover, there are National Institutes of Technical Teachers Training and Research, which hold training courses in technical and professional areas.

Required number of courses under career advancement scheme - As per UGC notification on "Revision of pay scales and minimum qualifications for appointment of teachers in universities and colleges and other measures for the maintenance of standards, 1998" for placement in senior scale, in addition to the other requirement in the guidelines, the lecturer should also participate in one orientation programme and one refresher course. (Those with Ph. D Degree would be exempted from one refresher course). As per the Gazette of India Notification dated September 18, 2010 regarding UGC regulations on minimum qualifications for appointment of teachers in Universities and Colleges and measures for the maintenance of standards in Higher Education, 2010, faculty development programmes have been linked to the Academic Performance Indicators (API) in Career Advancement Scheme (CAS). Under the present system, teachers

are awarded 20 points on successfully participating in the faculty development programmes for not less than two weeks duration and are awarded 10 points on successfully participating in the FDPs for one week duration.

Objectives of Research

As needs assessment enables institutions to determine the gap between existing and desired competencies, ensuring that FD programs are relevant, evidence-based, and aligned with institutional goals (Travis, 1993; Sorcinelli, Austin, Eddy, & Beach, 2006), the present study is guided by the following objectives:

- In view of the changed educational environment, what are the current knowledge enhancement needs that lead to professional development of the higher education faculty members?
- To identify key areas as per the priority of faculty members' perception that need to be included in FDPs for their professional development.
- To provide recommendations for designing evidence-based and contextually relevant faculty development programs.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study is conducted by using analytical and descriptive type of methodology. Questionnaire survey was used to study the training needs of higher education practitioners. After the pilot study questionnaire was refined and reformed on Likert Scale, which comprised different effectiveness dimensions of faculty development programmes.

Data Collection -450 questionnaires were distributed among the practitioners of higher education in various colleges and universities located in the capital city of Delhi during 2012. Only 359 questionnaires could be received back out of which 302 were found suitable for inclusion in the present study as rest of them were incomplete.

Reliability Analysis (Cronbach α) - Before any statistical analysis of the data, it is important to measure the reliability and validity of the instrument. The reliability of the scale was estimated by

calculating Cronbach's α . The α value obtained is .94, which indicates high reliability level of the scale.

Participants demographic profiles - Frequency analysis of the data discloses There are 150 male and 152 female participants in this study. 52% participants are from the age group 25–34. It is notable that usually people of this age group join as faculty members in the Higher Education Sector, and they are more career-oriented and work for career advancements. 37% participants are from the age group 35–44.

This is the time when people struggle for reaching the higher rungs of the professional hierarchy. Rest of the participants are from the age groups above 45 years. People belonging to this age group are usually those who are well established in their profession and are stable. 73% of the participants are Lecturer/Assistant Professor and 20% participants are Sr. Lecturers/Assistant Professors (Sr. Scale). Rest of the Participants are Associate Professors or Professors.

VI. ANALYSIS OF NEED FOR VARIOUS DIMENSIONS TO BE INCLUDED IN FDPs

The structured questionnaire on need of various areas to be included in the FDPs was based on 5-point Likert type scale. The value 5 was assigned to the highest perception, i.e., when the participants strongly agree to a given statement based on professional development needs.

Value 4 was assigned to the next higher perception, i.e., when the participants agree to a given statement in this regard. Value 3 was assigned to the neutral situation when participants neither agree nor disagree to a training need related statement. Value 2 was assigned to the participants' disagreement and value 1 being the least was assigned when participants strongly disagreed with a statement based on professional development need.

For the research objective I, i.e., in view of the changed educational environment, what are the current knowledge enhancement needs that lead to professional development of the higher education

faculty members, following hypotheses have been tested:

As per the perception of the Higher Education Faculty Members: –

H1: Class handling skill development for knowledge transfer is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H2: Knowledge enhancement on educational related subjects is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H3: Educational support activities related skill development for effective knowledge transfer is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H4: Knowledge acquisition for Professional Development is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H5: Technological skills development is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H6: Using technology for knowledge management is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H7: Knowledge creation through research is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H8: Assessment of knowledge through evaluation is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H9: Competency building is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H10: Personality development is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H11: Managerial skill development is needed to be included in the FDPs.

H12: Matters related to national development in which higher education can play a positive role are needed to be included in the FDPs.

H13: Present day challenges before the higher education system and their solution need to be included in the FDPs.

H14: Networking needs of faculty should be fulfilled through FDPs.

Hypotheses Testing for FDP Needs

In order to test the statistical significance at 95%, right-tailed z-test at test value 3 was used for ascertaining areas, which higher education faculty members perceive, needed to be included in the faculty development programmes (Table 5.8).

H0: $\mu \leq 3$

H1: $\mu > 3$

Table 1 – Hypotheses Testing for Need - One-

	Test Value = 3				Hypotheses supported/ not supported
	t (z statistic)*	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	
Class Handling Skills for Knowledge Transfer	21.451	297	.000	.99329	Supported
Knowledge Of Education Related Subjects	25.146	295	.000	.99578	Supported
Educational Support Activities for Effective Knowledge Transfer	20.980	298	.000	.90412	Supported
Knowledge Acquisition for Professional Development	43.270	300	.000	1.27159	Supported
Technological Skills for Knowledge Management	29.800	300	.000	1.16080	Supported
Using Technology for Knowledge Management	35.551	300	.000	1.25581	Supported
Knowledge Creation Through Research	46.033	300	.000	1.35596	Supported
Assessment Of Knowledge Through Evaluation	29.237	297	.000	1.17315	Supported
Competence Building	33.487	299	.000	1.29417	Supported
Personality Development	25.400	299	.000	1.03583	Supported
Managerial Skills	26.884	299	.000	1.03667	Supported
National Development and H.E.	32.882	301	.000	1.18212	Supported
Needs Because Of Challenges Before H.E.	38.227	300	.000	1.33887	Supported
Networking Needs for Knowledge Sharing	37.299	299	.000	1.17333	Supported

(Sample size being large t-test automatically gets converted into z test in SPSS)

The standard normal statistic for the given significance level, (α) of 0.05, Z_{α} is 1.64. (Malhotra& Dash 2009, Webster 2010). Since all the values of z statistics are greater than 1.64 (critical value for right tailed z test) at 95% level of significance, hypotheses are supported in all the areas presented in Table 1. Hence, on the basis of z-test it can be concluded that all the areas included in the questionnaire are perceived to be needed for faculty development programmes by the participants.

Priority of Areas to be Included in the FDPs

To know the perception of faculty members regarding their priorities for professional development, criteria of mean has been adopted. Mean ratings were calculated for each professional development need, which were then ranked. Various dimensions that needed to be included in the faculty development programmes were categorized on the following basis:

Areas with a mean score of 4.1 to 5.0 were considered to be highly needed

Areas with a mean score of 3.1 to 4.0 were considered to be needed

Areas with a mean score of 2.1 to 3.0 were considered moderately needed

Areas with a mean score of <2.0 were considered to be not needed.

Descriptive statistics in descending order of mean is presented below, which depicts the areas for FDPs in descending order of priority as per the perception of participants.

Table 2 – Priority of Needs

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Category
Knowledge Creation Through Research	4.3560	.51105	Highly needed
Needs Because Of Challenges Before H.E.	4.3389	.60764	Highly needed
Competence Building	4.2942	.66939	Highly needed
Knowledge Acquisition for Professional Development	4.2716	.50985	Highly needed
Using Technology for Knowledge Management	4.2558	.61285	Highly needed
National Development and H.E.	4.1821	.62475	Highly needed
Networking Needs for Knowledge Sharing	4.1733	.54486	Highly needed
Assessment Of Knowledge Through Evaluation	4.1732	.69269	Highly needed
Technological Skills for Knowledge Management	4.1608	.67581	Highly needed
Managerial Skills	4.0367	.66788	Highly needed
Personality Development	4.0358	.70634	Highly needed
Knowledge Of Education Related Subjects	3.9958	.68131	Needed
Class Handling Skills for Knowledge Transfer	3.9933	.79934	Needed

Educational Support Activities for Effective Knowledge Transfer	3.9041	.74517	Needed
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(The calculations are based on the actual data and no treatment of the missing has been done for this section of analysis.)

The above table indicates that knowledge and skills needed for effective transfer of knowledge to students, which include three areas, i.e., class handling, educational support activities and education-related subjects, have been perceived to be needed for inclusion in the FDPs by the higher education faculty members. All other areas, except these three, have been perceived to be highly needed for inclusion in the FDPs by the higher education faculty members.

VII. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION STATEMENT

The extensive quantitative survey, undertaken to explore the knowledge and skill enhancement needs of higher education faculty members through FDPs revealed following results:

- a) On the basis of mean values, it has been concluded that Indian Higher Education faculty members perceive following order of priorities for their FDP needs:
 - i. Knowledge creation through research and sharing the same
 - ii. Needs because of challenges before higher education
 - iii. Competence building
 - iv. Knowledge acquisition for professional development
 - v. Using technology for knowledge management
 - vi. National development and higher education
 - vii. Networking needs for knowledge sharing
 - viii. Assessment of knowledge through evaluation
 - ix. Technological skills for knowledge management
 - x. Managerial skills
 - xi. Personality development
 - xii. Knowledge of education related subjects
 - xiii. Class handling skills for knowledge transfer

- xiv. Educational support activities for effective knowledge transfer.

Statistical testing at 95% level of significance by applying right tailed z-test at test value 3, supported the hypotheses that all the above-mentioned areas are perceived as needed to be included in the FDPs by the higher education faculty members.

In the study of Pearson and Thomas (2010) based on their 2008 survey, the most important goal for their professional development was ranked to increase their productivity in research. Further the faculty expressed the most interesting goal for their professional development as maintaining the in-depth knowledge and expertise in their area of specialization.

The qualitative study conducted by Dutta Jayanti (2010) also revealed 58 themes including training needs for self (Professional and Personal) covering pedagogical skills, personality development, administrative skills, research skills, managerial skills needs to learn dealing with students, and needs for societal understanding including the relevant portions of history economics political system philosophy, scientific trends, environment functioning of UGC, educational policies, examination, evaluation, and challenges of education in India.

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